

PROMOTING ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH ENERGY TRANSITION, NATURAL RESOURCE RENT AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: EVIDENCE FROM SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA(SSA)

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Abstract

Accelerating Africa's energy transition is key to achieving sustainable environment amidst recent global energy crisis. This study investigates the impact of energy transition on environmental sustainability in sub-Saharan Africa with special interest on the role economic growth plays for the period 2000 to 2020. Employing Instrumental Variable – Generalised Method of Moments (IV-GMM) approach and a two-stage least squares method for robustness check, results indicate that renewable energy consumption (rec) exerts a negative and significant impact on carbon emission while renewable electricity output (reo) exerts a negative but non-significant influence on CO₂ in SSA for the first model while renewable energy consumption (rec), renewable electricity output (reo) exhibited negative and significant impact on environmental sustainability for the second model. Income level in SSA for the two models favours non-renewable energy consumption and deteriorates the environment. We recommend balanced transformative decarbonization until income threshold improves to impact positively on environment sustainability.

Keywords: *Energy transition, environmental sustainability, economic growth, renewable energy*

1. INTRODUCTION

Preserving the environment is not only important as a life-supporting platform and platform to support economic activities for the present generation but also for the future generation. For this reason, environmental sustainability is viewed as one of the three pillars of sustainable development. Its importance is also connected to the fact that eight of the United Nations' 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are directly or indirectly linked to the environment. In 2021, there has been a significant increase in greenhouse gas emissions (IEA, 2021b) and significant extreme weather events worldwide. In 2022, the environmental quality became more threatened because it witnessed some of the most extreme weather events in history, striking many more countries on a much more regular basis, with ever more significant impacts on populations and economies (IEA, 2023d). Global business leaders have identified natural disasters and extreme weather events as being in the top 10 perceived risks for the medium- and long-term (WEF, 2023). Energy-related activities accounted for around 73 percent of global greenhouse gas emissions in 2016 as could be seen in Figure 1 (IEA, 2023d). This includes emissions from burning fossil fuels in the electricity sector, heating and cooling, and transport and manufacturing.

Figure 1: Global Green House Gas emission, 2016
Source: IEA, 2023d

On average, greenhouse gas emissions in African countries grew more slowly than in other developing economies from 2008 to 2017. The electricity sector is responsible for the largest share of energy-related CO₂ emissions in Africa, at around 42 percent of the total in 2018 (IRENA, 2023c).

Figure 2: Share of energy-related CO₂ emissions in Africa by sector, 2018
Source: IEA, 2023d

This situation is complicated by the fact that Africa has one of the highest rates of population growth in the world, and contains some of the world’s poorest countries (World Bank, 2022). Africa needs to make the transition from traditional to conventional sources of energy. According to Cavard (1989), energy transition is the process whereby there is an increase in the volume and proportion of commercial energy to the extent that it replaces traditional fuels as the main energy source. As aptly observed by IMF, (2022d), overcoming the various energy and environmental problems facing Africa requires the provision and utilization of higher-quality fuels, resulting in a more balanced energy mix. This, however, raises the pertinent question of how to achieve an increase in commercial energy consumption vis-à-vis traditional energy without adversely affecting the continent’s already fragile ecosystem, given that the production and consumption of commercial energy are major contributors to greenhouse gases.

Kahsai et al. (2012) empirically reviewed the growth-energy consumption nexus in Sub-Saharan Africa. They concluded that in the long run, there is evidence of energy consumption supporting economic growth, and growth increasing energy consumption. A recent study found that a 1 percent increase in renewable energy consumption is expected to lead in Africa to a growth of 0.07 percent in the short run, and a robust 1.9 percent in the long run (Qudrat-Ullah and Nevo, 2021). The UN High-Level Dialogue on Energy in 2021, through the theme report on Enabling SDGs through Inclusive Just Energy Transition stated that “energy is inextricably linked to virtually all the SDGs and transforming the world’s energy systems will create new jobs, advance gender equality, and empower people, communities, and societies” (UN, 2021a).

This study is significant because the infrastructure development gap is tied to growth in income, which further affects the level of energy consumption, whether renewable or non-renewable, thus, affecting the speed of energy transition and environmental sustainability. Cavard, (1989) argued that inter-country variations in the energy transition process mirror differences in economic growth, level of urbanization, energy exporter status of the country, extent of forest and woodland resources, and incidence of poverty. Therefore, the economic index for Africa is also a reflection of the relative share of the energy sector in the overall economy with implications on environmental sustainability (IRENA, 2021a).

Figure 3 reflects the annual growth rate of GDP of sub-Saharan African countries, which although varies exhibits a downward general trend.

Fig. 3: Real GDP Growth Rate (Annual %) of sub-Saharan African
Source: World Bank, 2022

This general downward trend of GDP in Africa holds some implications on the nexus between energy transition and environmental sustainability in Africa as posited by Cavard, (1989) and (IRENA, 2021a). Therefore, this paper, in particular, hypothesizes that inter-country variations in the level of economic growth have implications on how energy transition affects the achievement of a sustainable environment. This study is, therefore, significant because it empirically investigated if this theoretical postulation by Cavard, (1989) holds for Africa. Furthermore, from the literature reviewed, extensive studies have been carried out on the relationship between energy transition and environmental quality in sub-Saharan Africa with varying outcomes of insignificant relationships, positive and negative significant relationships respectively. These divergent conclusions by scholars could be attributed to the proxies adopted for environmental quality and energy transition. This present study introduces two measures of environmental quality (CO₂ and ecological footprint) and energy transition (renewable energy consumption and renewable electricity output) with income playing a moderating or enhancing role for robust analysis and effective and efficient policy prescriptions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical Literature Review

Theoretically, the relationship between energy transition and environmental sustainability is captured in the revised neoclassical theory of environmental sustainability popularized by the individual works of Boulding (1966) and Dragulanescu and Dragulanescu (2013). The theory posits that the economic system is a complex web comprising two distinct economies: first, the real economy, which is part of the economic system made up of economic activities and value creation, as well as effective allocation and distribution of scarce resources; second, the extended economy, which supports life on earth; that part of the ecosystem that recognizes the interdependence between the economy and the environment. They further added that the real economy is an open and circular subsystem that can only function effectively with the support of its ecological foundation – the environment. This imposes the need to maintain a balance between the two economies to ensure the sustainability of both economic and environmental resources.

2.2. Empirical Literature Review

Some empirical studies have been carried out to investigate the impact of energy transition on environmental sustainability in Africa and other parts of the world. For instance, Samson, (2023) Muddassar, Sobia, and Muhammad (2022), Mulugeta, et al, (2023). Chunjiao, and Hongxi (2023) found that economic growth is the leading factor of consumption-based carbon emission while electricity from [renewable resources](#), research and development in renewable energy, environmental-related [taxes](#), and development of environmental-related [technologies](#) substantially reduce consumption-based emissions while encouraging environmental sustainability. The income factor amongst other gaps are investigated.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Data

This study used annual data for environmental sustainability indicators (carbon dioxide emission and ecological footprint), and energy transition indicators (renewable energy consumption, renewable electricity output). Other variables used are GDP per capita (following the EKC

Hypothesis), natural resource rent, urbanization, and globalization. Carbon emission and ecological footprint were adopted as dependent variables following existing environmental sustainability literature (Gao and Chen, 2023); Ahmad et al, 2023; and Abbasi et al, (2021). In line with Chien, et al. (2023) and Udemba and Tosun (2022), we used renewable energy consumption and renewable electricity output to measure energy transition. In line with Wang and Razzaq (2022), total natural resource rent is included in the study to account for the effect of natural resources on environmental quality. Finally, globalization and urbanization are equally included in the model to recognize the critical effect of globalization and urbanization on environmental sustainability (Sarraz, Naseem, and Mohsim (2022).

3.2. Model specification

Following the works of Samson, (2023); Muddassar, Sobia, Muhammad (2022); and Ibrahim, et al, (2022), we present carbon emission (C0_2) and ecological footprint (EFP) as functions of renewable energy consumption (REC), renewable electricity output (REO), and a set of control variables (X) which exhibit a more predictive power towards environmental sustainability variables – natural resource rents, Gross Domestic Product Per Capita (GDPC), globalization (GLO) and Urbanization (URB) and this accounts for our objective. Hence the model is specified as:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \delta X_{it} + \theta Z_{it} + \gamma_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where, i and t denote nations and years, respectively. Y is the energy transition indicators, X stands for the vector of our key variables (REC and REO),and Z denotes a vector of control variables; γ and ε are country fixed effect and white noise assumptions respectively. In this study, we predict that $\delta < 0$, that is to say, the key explanatory variables are expected to have a reducing effect on environmental indicators. We selected control variables (Z) taking into account natural resource rent (NRRT), GDPC, GLO, and URB. The parameter estimates and their respective economic expectations are $\theta > 0$. This means that the variables are expected to trigger environmental degradation. Details of all our variables are captured in Table 1.

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This study employed IV-GMM which is presented in Table 1 below. Using carbon dioxide emission as an indicator for environmental sustainability (model 1), we found that energy transition such as renewable energy consumption (rec) exerts a negative and significant impact on carbon emission while renewable electricity output (reo) exerts a negative but insignificant influence on C0_2 in SSA. Specifically, a percent rise in the use of REC reduces carbon emissions by 0.33%. The negative and significant linkage between renewable energy consumption and carbon emission aligns with the findings of Ibrahim, et al, (2022), but against the findings of Samson, (2023) and Muddassar, Sobia, Muhammad (2022). Natural resource rent (NRRT), economic growth (GDPC), and urbanization (URB) have positive and significant influences on carbon emissions. The outcome of the relationship between natural resource rent and carbon emission corroborates with the findings of Mahmood, Zahoor, Sana, and Rafael (2023). This implies that a percent rise in NRRT, GDP, and URB endangers environmental quality. The outcome of NRRT and CO_2 attunes to the findings of Mahmood, Zahoor, Sana, and Rafael (2023). Also, the globalization index (GLO) has a positive but insignificant impact on C0_2 in SSA.

Table 1: Result of IVGMM TWO-STEP SYSTEM (Dependent variables = C0_2 and EFP)

	<i>MODEL 1(C0_2)</i>	<i>MODEL 2 (EFP)</i>
<i>Variables</i>	coef	coef
<i>rec</i>	-0.333** [0.158]	-0.218*** [0.072]
<i>reo</i>	-0.020 [0.025]	-0.020** [0.010]
<i>Nrrt</i>	0.381*** [0.050]	0.014 [0.018]
<i>gdpc</i>	0.528*** [0.130]	0.199*** [0.061]
<i>glo</i>	2.586 [1.669]	0.545 [0.742]
<i>Urb</i>	0.465*** [0.093]	-0.202*** [0.051]
<i>Constant</i>	-15.665** [6.226]	-2.066 [2.796]
<i>Diagnostics tests:</i>		
<i>Kleibergen-Paaprk LM statistic</i>	5.514	5.175
<i>p-value</i>	0.227	0.127
<i>Crag-Donald Wald F-Statistic</i>	4.618	4.618
<i>Kleibergen-Paaprk Wald F statistic</i>	2.380	2.380
<i>Hansen J statistic</i>	0.276	3.110
<i>p-value</i>	0.871	0.211
<i>Observations</i>	647	647
<i>R²</i>	0.755	0.500

Source: Author's computation, 2024

From Model 2, which used ecological footprint as an indicator for environmental sustainability, findings indicate that renewable energy consumption (*rec*), renewable electricity output (*reo*), and urbanization (*urb*) exhibited negative and significant linkages with environmental sustainability in Sub-Saharan Africa within the period under study. This means that a percent increase in *rec*, *reo*, and *urb* enhances environmental sustainability by reducing ecological footprint by 0.22%, 0.02%, and 0.20% respectively. This result is in tandem with the findings of Ansari et al. (2021); Raihan and Tuspekova (2022); Yang et al. (2021); and Qayyum et al. (2021) but contrary to the findings of Mohsin et al. (2021). GDPC exerts a positive and significant impact on ecological footprint and by implication rise in income degrades the environment in SSA.

Following the predictions of the EKC Hypothesis, findings indicate that GDPPC has a positive nexus with environmental sustainability variables. This implies that GDPPC within the period under review has a debilitating effect on the environment. This is not surprising given the overall trend in GDP growth rate evidenced in Figure 3. This situation is critical to energy transition given the fact that many countries in SSA still grapple with rising poverty levels and infrastructure gaps necessitating the pursuit of economic growth, of which the use of non-renewable energy could be inevitable.

From the stand point of the EKC Hypothesis, a positive linkage between economic growth and environmental degradation implies that Africa is yet to approach the income threshold that is capable of pushing energy consumers from non-renewable energy consumption to renewable energy consumption. Although energy transition variables have significant mitigating impacts on environmental degradation when the ecological footprint is used to represent environmental sustainability, the impacts are very small given that the energy transition index for developed countries is high.

Furthermore, to test the viability of the IV-GMM technique, we called in aid four diagnostic tests such as the Kleibergen-Paaprk LM statistic, Crag-Donald Wald F-Statistic, Kleibergen-Paaprk Wald F statistic, and Hansen J statistic. The results revealed that our estimates are free from invalid instrument issues. With the assumption of an under-identified model, the Stock-Write LM test indicates that the coefficient on the change in the explanatory variable is equal to zero and the over-identifying constraints are valid across specified models. Thus, the J- Hansen statistic also validates the accuracy of the estimating instruments. The coefficient of multiple determinations R^2 , which measures the changes in the dependent variable explained by the explanatory variables are 0.755 and 0,500 for the two models. This entails that about 76% and 50% of variations in the dependent variables are explained by the independent variables across the two models.

We tested and confirmed the reliability and robustness of our estimates by implementing the two-stage least square (2SLS) estimation, which takes care of endogeneity issues just like IV-GMM. The outcome of 2SLS estimation also confirms a similar result with the IV-GMM regression model (see Table 2).

Table 2: Two-Stage Least Square Estimation (Dependent Variable = CO₂ and EFP)

	<i>MODEL 1</i>	<i>MODEL 2</i>
<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coef</i>	<i>Coef</i>
<i>rec</i>	-0.328** [0.169]	-0.207*** [0.076]
<i>reo</i>	-0.022 [0.028]	-0.022** [0.013]
<i>nrrt</i>	0.384*** [0.046]	0.019 [0.021]
<i>gdpc</i>	0.524*** [0.127]	0.184*** [0.057]
<i>Glo</i>	2.659 [1.653]	-0.218 [0.043]
<i>Urb</i>	0.464*** [0.096]	-0.202*** [0.051]
<i>Constant</i>	-15.938** [6.226]	-2.690 [2.788]
<i>Diagnostics tests:</i>		
<i>Anderson canon. corr. LM statistic</i>	13.752	13.752
<i>p-value</i>	0.0033	0.003
<i>Crag-Donald Wald F-Statistic</i>	4.618	4.618
<i>F*</i>	164.93	73.65
<i>Prob> F</i>	0.000	0.000
<i>Sargan statistic</i>	0.334	3.135

<i>p-value</i>	0.846	0.209
<i>Observations</i>	647	647
<i>R²</i>	0.7537	0.4832

Author's computation, 2024

5. CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATION

This study investigated the nexus between energy transition and environmental sustainability and the role economic growth plays in this nexus. The study is relevant because it can serve as a mirror of reflection through which Africa can see itself and thus, help in repositioning Africa in the fight to achieve a sustainable environment. Africa, no doubt, has abundant renewable energy resources and is therefore well placed to meet the electricity demands of its growing population and economies with clean, affordable electricity for a favorable impact on environmental sustainability. However, each country has different socio-economic starting points, which will take them down different paths in the energy transition and environmental sustainability path. This study concludes that the actual pace and eventual outcomes of the impact of the energy transition on environmental sustainability will be partly determined by each country's current level of income, dependence on non-renewable energy sources, urbanization, and natural resource rent. Economic growth is critical in the nexus between energy transition and environmental sustainability in SSA because SSA still pursues economic development as a macroeconomic objective to solve issues of poverty. This is where the balanced energy mix by IMF, (2022d), comes into play as an interim measure for SSA to overcome the various energy and environmental problems facing Africa. To achieve a secure, equitable, and sustainable environment, SSA needs to take steps to innovate, support education and build human capital, strengthen energy regulations and political commitment, and provide finance for investment in renewable energy sources.

We also recommend the building of necessary human capacity and skills within African countries to enable them undertake energy transitions on their terms while also boosting economic growth and job creation on the continent.

Energy transition has the potential to drive broad socio-economic development. We recommend energy policies to foster balanced transformative decarbonization until the income threshold improves the environment.

As developing economies expand, electricity demand increases. In short, economic growth in developing countries increases consumptive electricity demand because households earn more income and choose to spend some of it on electricity and appliances. We recommend that SSA should finance and invest in innovations to harvest the abundant renewable energy potentials since Africa arguably has the largest renewable energy resources of any continent.

SSA should build functional, competent institutions and human capital to drive the energy transition process.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FURTHER STUDIES

Data for some variables in sub-Saharan Africa were unavailable prompting the reduction in countries within Sub-Saharan Africa. Non-inclusion of some countries could have some level of impact on the outcome of the result. We suggest that a comparison between advanced countries and Africa be done.

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Appendix 1: The Study Sample (29 SSA Nations)

Angola, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Cabo Verde, Cameroon, Central Africa Republic, Congo Republic, Cote d'Ivoire, Eswatini, Ethiopia, Gabon, Ghana, Guinea, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Mali, Mauritius, Mozambique, Namibia, Niger, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao Tome & Principe, Senegal, Sierra Leon, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe

Appendix 2

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF).

<i>variables</i>	<i>C0_2</i>		<i>EFP</i>	
	<i>VIF</i>	<i>1/VIF</i>	<i>VIF</i>	<i>1/VIF</i>
<i>REC</i>	3.07	0.326	3.07	0.326116
<i>REO</i>	1.29	0.775	1.29	0.775
<i>NRRT</i>	1.74	0.574	1.74	0.574
<i>GDPC</i>	2.77	0.361	2.77	0.361
<i>GLO</i>	1.75	0.571	1.75	0.571
<i>URB</i>	1.94	0.514	1.94	0.514
<i>Mean VIF</i>	2.09		2.09	

Source: Authors Computation

N/B: Theoretically, if VIF is greater than 10 and the Average